

EXPLORING LANGUAGE BARRIER CHALLENGES: LIVED EXPERIENCES OF BSED-ENGLISH BLAAN STUDENTS IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

Language barriers cause significant challenges and hinder Blaan students in learning English while pursuing a Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) major in English. This qualitative study explores the lived experiences of five (5) BSED-English Blaan students enrolled at Green Valley College Foundation, Incorporated, focusing on language barriers in learning English. The study examines how these barriers affect the English language journey of Blaan students through well-organized interviews and thematic analysis, highlighting their experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms. The findings reveal two main themes: (1) Lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar awareness; and (2) Challenges in communication in diverse cultures. These insights emphasize the various language barriers Blaan students face and highlight the importance of providing support and tools to help them learn English and understand different cultures, thereby avoiding miscommunication and misunderstandings.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

In the pursuit of understanding the complex dynamics of language learning, especially in educational settings, it was crucial to explore Blaan students' lived experiences. The most obvious effects of language barriers in the classroom are the possible impacts on academic performance and communication tools. In the classroom, a student whose primary language is not spoken by the teacher may find it difficult to understand instructions and concepts, and they may require additional time and help to complete assignments (Antezana, 2023).

Since the Angolan Civil War ended in 2002, a sizable multilingual and multicultural workforce from several countries, including Portugal, Cuba, China, Vietnam, India, Brazil, and Zimbabwe, has been welcomed into Angola. Despite the need, there are currently no studies that cover intercultural communication or "language barriers" in general for the Angolan setting. These studies are particularly needed in many social science sectors with a focus on health, business, and education. Recent years have seen a surge in interest in the social science field of communication barriers among academics studying education, linguistics, and business (Da

Costa, 2021). As quoted by Dută (2015), “the theme of communication in higher education has been, and will continue to be, a topic of interest and significant contributions have been made in this respect, concretized in many studies and publications.”

The Philippines is regarded as one of the largest English-speaking nations. English is currently included as one of the Philippines' official languages in the country's constitution. It is the official language of commerce, science, technology, government, and worldwide communication, as well as the primary medium of instruction in schools (Cabigon, 2015 as cited in the study of Santos, Fernandez, and Ilustre, 2022). According to Marinas (2021) as cited in the study of Santos, Fernandez, and Ilustre (2022), the Philippines is also one of the top locations for ESL students, with two-thirds of the population speaking English fluently. However, Filipinos continue to struggle with academic language related to language barriers when learning English, particularly college students.

Communication between people with different linguistic backgrounds is severely hampered by language challenges, which are especially problematic in educational environments such as Green Valley College Foundation, Incorporated, which has a diverse culture and experiences language barriers because students speak different languages. Bloon language limitations frequently hinder communication, making it difficult to have a fluid exchange of ideas. It has been said that language limitations can lead to miscommunication and make it harder to collaborate (Gudykunst and Kim, 2017).

Hence, this study aimed to provide insights into the experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of Bloon students in learning English, while exploring language barrier challenges. Understanding these challenges could help educators adapt teaching methods to better support future English learners. Additionally, in today's globalized world where English proficiency is often a requirement for academic and professional success, insights from this study can contribute to improving language education programs and addressing language barriers more effectively.

Literature Review

This section presents the related literature and studies after a thorough and detailed search by the researchers, which are important for the variables included in the research. It focuses on the literature about (1) language barriers, (2) acquiring language, (3) language barriers and coping mechanisms, and (4) students' experiences with language barriers.

Language Barriers

According to Buarqoub (2019), communication is the process of exchanging thoughts, feelings, information, facts, views, and emotions between a sender and a recipient. The goal of effective communication is to change the knowledge, attitude, and behavior of the recipient by delivering the right message through the right channel at the right time. One of the factors that prevent individuals from understanding one another is the language barrier. Language barriers are a common challenge for people, organizations, governments, multinational corporations, states, and the entire world.

Language barriers can cause miscommunication issues, including misunderstandings, misinterpretations, distorted messages, misinformation, confusion, mistrust, uncertainty, frustration, and inadequate or incorrect feedback. They can also result in aviation and marine accidents and disasters, fatalities, tension, conflict, and violence among people. These barriers can impede efficient communication (Buarqoub, 2019).

Acquiring Language

The process of learning a language involves using different strategies and methods to improve language skills. Blaan students studying for a Bachelor of Science in Education (BSED) with an English major often participate in immersive language learning activities like language courses, linguistic workshops, and practical teaching opportunities (Banks, 2016).

Furthermore, research emphasizes the effectiveness of communicative language teaching methods. These methods focus on real-life communication and interaction to help students learn languages (Richards and Rodgers, 2014).

However, despite these efforts, Blaan students may face challenges such as limited exposure to real-life language use and difficulties in understanding cultural and language differences (Dörnyei and Ushioda, 2019).

Language Barrier and Coping Mechanisms

Considering the importance of communication between non-native speakers and members of the host community, it's crucial to discuss adaptive methods that existed before the use of technology. One such method is pretending, defined as a face-to-face tactic used in cross-cultural communication to overcome language barriers during conversations. Pretending helps integrate international students into conversations, considering their concerns for self-image, others' perceptions, and mutual respect (Teriu, 2012 as cited in the study by Elaga and Özad, 2017).

Another tactic used by international students to overcome language barriers is nonverbal communication, which involves conveying information without speaking. This includes eye contact, gestures, personal space, clothing, physical cues, and intonation. According to Elaga (2015) as cited in the study by Elaga and Özad (2017), international students rely on nonverbal cues like eye contact, gestures, signs, touch, facial expressions, and intonation to enhance communication with members of the host community.

Students Experiences in Language Barriers

Inadequate language skills in educational settings can lead to both positive and negative experiences, as well as poor learning outcomes, posing challenges for students (Awe, 2014). Language barriers make online lectures difficult for international students (Ali, Yoenanto, and Nurdibyanandaru, 2020).

Limited English proficiency can sometimes cause a professor to have a negative perception of a student's readiness for class. Language skills have also been identified as a challenge between teachers and their international students in another study (Wu, Garza, and Guzman, 2015).

According to Kusgey and Mukaka (2018), international students, particularly Filipino-Americans and Africans, can speak and understand English, but they struggle and feel stressed when they can't follow conversations, especially when professors explain things using Philippines-specific dialects.

Theoretical Lens

This study was guided by Sociocultural Theory proposed by Lev Vygotsky and Communicative Competence Theory coined by Dell Hymes. According to Sociocultural Theory, language development is closely tied to social interactions and cultural influences. Therefore,

exploring how students manage language barriers within their social and cultural contexts can offer valuable insights into their learning experiences. This theory highlights the role of social interaction and cultural background in learning (Macleod, 2024).

Communicative Competence Theory, as developed by Dell Hymes, extends beyond linguistic skills to include the ability to use language effectively in various social and cultural settings. It comprises four components: linguistic competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence, and strategic competence (Kugai, 2022).

By applying the framework of communicative competence, we gained insights into the unique linguistic, sociocultural, and strategic challenges faced by BSED-English Blaan students in their English language learning journey. This approach helped us analyze how social interactions, cultural influences, and language usage influenced the students' learning experiences, providing a deeper understanding of the complex dynamics of language acquisition in educational settings.

Research Objectives

This study aims to analyze and explore language barrier challenges in the lived experiences of BSED-English Blaan students in learning English. Specifically, it seeks to:

1. Examine the lived experiences of Blaan students in learning English in relation to language barriers.
2. Identify the challenges faced by Blaan students in learning English due to language barriers.
3. Explore the coping mechanisms employed by Blaan students to overcome language barriers in learning English.

Significance of the Study

This study was conducted to determine the concept behind the experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the participants in learning English in terms of language barriers.

This study was deemed significant for the following:

Students. This study helps them to analyze the situation when it comes to learning English in terms of language barriers in school.

Teachers. The result of this study helps them to establish a good learning environment where every student can learn and understand their lesson without any language barriers and help their students improve their communication skills and this will give them awareness about the learning capacity of their students when it comes to learning English.

School Administration. This study was also helpful to the administration in coming up with strategies to encourage students to learn different languages by fostering a good relationship between students and teachers as well as the administration to improve the communication skills of their students to maximize learning despite the challenges encountered by some students in terms of language barriers in learning English.

Future Researchers. They could use the result of this study as their guide or reference for conducting a study about learning English in terms of language barriers. This study would give them confidence to expand their knowledge and skills in the field of education and the advancement of the research process. This research would be helpful to future researchers in

developing an enhanced curriculum more effective and responsive to every student's unique needs when it comes to learning.

METHODS

Research Design

To determine the practicability of the study, the researchers used a certain measure. The research approach used is phenomenological under qualitative research. A phenomenological research approach was employed in this study to gain insights into student's experiences in learning English. This research study aimed to help the readers learn and understand the lived experiences of BSED-English Blaan students in learning English in terms of language barriers. Qualitative research pursued to gain insights and understand people's experiences and perspectives by studying social organizations and human behavior (Girardin, 2023). Phenomenological research is a qualitative research approach that focused on exploring the subjective experiences and perspectives of individuals. Phenomenological research approach aimed to understand how people make meaning of their experiences and how they interpret the world around them (Eckel, 2023).

Setting

This study was conducted in Green Valley College Foundation, Inc., located at Km. 2, Bo.2, Gensan Drive, Koronadal City, South Cotabato. Green Valley College Foundation, Incorporated (formerly Green Valley School of Arts and Technology) is a private, non-sectarian educational institution in Koronadal City, South Cotabato. It was started in 1995 by Engr. Romeo Sustiguer who was managing Green Valley Machinery. As a response to the need for more workers, Engr. Sustiguer established the school which provided technical courses. Eventually, Green Valley's student population increased, and so it also began offering collegiate courses.

Currently, GVC offers associate and bachelor's degree programs in Teacher Education, Management, Engineering, and Information Technology. The school is also an accredited TESDA Training and Assessment Center, offering TVET courses like Computer Systems Servicing, Heavy Equipment Operation, and Shielded Metal Arc Welding. Green Valley College also has a Senior High School department providing the Academic and the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) tracks.

The School of Education is one of the fastest growing academic units, aspires to produce a strong pool of global educators. The environment provides for a conducive training ground for values oriented and excellent teachers which are exposed to learning and teaching innovations and are challenged to be a more progressive and proactive type of teacher.

The Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English is a four-year degree program that combines theory and practice designed to prepare students for teaching in secondary schools. Majors offered in this college are English and Technology and Livelihood Education.

Respondents

In selecting respondents for the research on "The Influence of Social Media on Academic Performance of BEED Students," several criteria were considered to ensure the relevance and reliability of the study findings.

Firstly, respondents were undergraduate students who were enrolled in the second semester of the 2023–2024 academic year in Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) programs in Green Valley College Foundation, Inc. This ensure that the student focused specifically on individuals pursuing teaching careers at the elementary level, whose academic performance is of particular interest. Additionally, respondents were actively engaged in their academic pursuits as indicated by enrollment in a minimum of eight subjects or courses during the current academic term. This criterion ensured that respondents had a substantial academic workload, providing sufficient data points to assess the potential impact of social media usage on academic performance across multiple subjects. Furthermore, respondents demonstrated regular engagement with social media platforms. This was confirmed through self-reported data or usage logs indicating consistent and active participation in social media activities, such as posting updates, engaging with content, and communicating with peers. By applying these criteria, the research aimed to capture a diverse yet relevant sample of BEED students who are actively navigating the demands of their academic curriculum while concurrently engaging with social media platforms. This approach facilitated a comprehensive examination of the relationship between social media usage patterns and academic performance within the context of the BEED program, providing valuable insights for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders concerned with optimizing student learning outcomes in teacher education programs.

Participants

The participants in this study were Blaan students from Green Valley College Foundation, Inc. The researchers used snowball sampling and purposive sampling techniques to select them. Snowball sampling involved asking initial participants to recommend others, while purposive sampling selected participants based on specific criteria set by the researchers.

The criteria for selection were straightforward: participants had to be BSED-English students enrolled at Green Valley College Foundation, Inc. for the academic year 2023-2024, they had to be Blaan, and they had to be either half-blooded or full-blooded Blaan. In total, five (5) BSED-English Blaan students were chosen to participate in the study.

Research Instrument

An interview guide was the appropriate method for collecting information because it enabled the researchers to formulate generalizations by obtaining firsthand data. The researchers opted to use this research method to generate conclusions for the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

Preparatory Phase

The researchers developed interview questions and obtained approval from their research adviser and validator before conducting interviews.

Data Collection Phase

A trial of the interview questions was conducted with a small sample to refine them. Participants were selected based on predefined criteria for diversity. During interviews, the researchers ensured consistency, clarity, and accuracy in data collection.

Data Processing Phase

After interviews, responses were transcribed or entered into a structured format with confidentiality. Transcripts were reviewed for errors and organized by themes or patterns. This prepared data for analysis.

Data Analysis Phase

Interview data was analyzed to identify recurring themes and patterns relevant to research questions. Findings were interpreted and validated through triangulation with other data sources or participant feedback.

Reporting Phase

Researchers documented the interview process, findings, and interpretations in a comprehensive report. They presented findings to the data analyst and sought approval before dissemination.

Review and Feedback Phase

Feedback from the adviser and panelists was incorporated into the final report. The document was revised for clarity, coherence, and accuracy, obtaining final approval before dissemination to the academic or professional community.

Data Analysis

This study used thematic analysis to explore language barrier challenges faced by BSED-English students during their language learning journey. The researchers followed Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis framework, starting with a comprehensive review of collected data, including interview transcripts and field notes. Initial coding was used to identify significant features and patterns, assigning codes to segments that reflected meaningful aspects of participants' experiences. These initial codes were then organized into potential themes, which were refined through a process of review and revision to accurately capture the data's essence.

The study emphasized the complexity of issues as perceived and expressed by the students themselves. Thematic analysis uncovered recurring themes, observations, and insights that illuminated the intricate nature of language barriers in educational settings. The choice of thematic analysis for this study was based on its flexibility and ability to reveal meaningful patterns in qualitative data. This approach facilitated systematic identification, analysis, and interpretation of themes, offering valuable insights into participants' viewpoints and experiences.

Scope and Limitation

This study aimed to understand the experience of learning English and the language barriers among BSED-English Blaen Students at Green Valley College Foundation, Incorporated, located in Km.2 Bo. 2, Gensan Drive, Koronadal City, South Cotabato. The researchers used a combination of snowball and purposive sampling techniques to select participants.

Snowball sampling involved current participants recommending others for the study. Purposive sampling was based on specific criteria set by the researchers: participants had to be BSED-English students enrolled at Green Valley College Foundation, Inc. for the academic year 2023-2024, and they had to be Blaen, either half-blooded or full-blooded. In total, five (5) BSED-English Blaen students were chosen.

Despite the study's limitations, it aimed to provide valuable insights into the experiences of Blaen students in the BSED-English program, laying the groundwork for further research in this field.

Ethical Consideration

Before conducting the study, participants were provided with detailed information about the study's purpose. Through informed consent, participants willingly decided to participate. To ensure confidentiality and prevent potential harm, all information was handled with utmost secrecy, adhering to RA 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act, which safeguards the identities of research participants.

Special care was taken to protect vulnerable populations such as children, the elderly, and those with diminished autonomy, ensuring their rights and welfare were safeguarded throughout the study. Research findings were reported accurately and honestly, without falsification or fabrication of data. The research paper will transparently document the methodology, findings, limitations, and implications, facilitating independent verification and replication of the study.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This chapter systematically presented, analyzed, and interpreted data obtained from interviews with selected BSED-English Blaan students regarding their experiences with language barriers in learning English. Each participant responded to five comprehensive questions aimed at understanding their challenges, experiences, and coping mechanisms. The chapter also encapsulated the research's conclusion and recommendation, summarizing key findings and drawing broader insights from the gathered data.

Table 1. Lived experiences of Blaan students in learning English in terms of language barriers.

PARTICIPANTS CODE	SIGNIFICANT STATEMENT	CONCEPTS	CATEGORY
MK	<i>... Maybe as a Blaan, the first thing we experience in studying English is a challenge in language barrier.... Sometimes, here we struggle with the right pronunciation of words... using the right sentences.....</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges in communication in diverse culture. Lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar awareness. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar awareness.
RB	<i>... It's not really easy sometimes to learn English, we're BSED student we faced a bit hard in in on how to pronounce especially if you only have small vocabulary, there will really have language barrier in learning and communication.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar awareness. 	
AB	<i>Actually, I'm not really fluent in English... when it comes in language barrier I</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of vocabulary awareness. 	

	<i>guess, there are words that I cannot understand or has a deep meaning that's why I'm struggling to understand it.</i>		
AS	<i>... some of the challenges I experience in learning English, particularly with language barriers are the deep vocabulary or some unfamiliar words to me... it prevents me to learn English or it gives me some... difficult of time or difficulties in learning English.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facing difficulties in learning English due to language barriers, particularly with unfamiliar vocabulary and pronunciation. 	
EQ	<i>... my experiences in learning English... was very difficult and challenging especially when it comes to language barriers,... I am having a hard time in understanding deep words and also when it comes to my pronunciation.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of vocabulary awareness and pronunciation 	

One emergent theme was generated from the data in Table 1: 1) Lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar awareness.

The theme was the lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar awareness. Participants MK, RB, and EQ, a full-blooded blaán, and participants AB and AS, a half-blooded blaán, shared their experiences in learning English due to a lack of knowledge in vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar. Participant AS also stated that speaking some incorrect words lowers her self-confidence because some people will laugh at her, especially if she mispronounces the words instead of helping or correcting her pronunciation.

Additionally, participants MK, RB, AB, AS, and EQ shared how they struggle with vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar. Participant MK stated that, as a Blaán student, she struggles most with using words, how to pronounce the word and grammar.

Moreover, participants MK and RB also stated that a lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar awareness can lead to confusion or will lead to miscommunication. In the same scenario, participant AB also recalled that vocabulary and pronunciation challenged them to learn English. Awe (2014) stated that inadequate language proficiency in educational settings can lead to both positive and negative experiences, impacting learning outcomes significantly. This aligns with the experiences recounted by participant MK, RB, AB, AS, and EQ who stated that a lack of

vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation of words prevented them from learning English and communicating, which leads to creating language barriers.

Table 2. Challenges of Blaan students in learning English in terms of language barriers.

PARTICIPANTS CODE	SIGNIFICANT STATEMENT	CONCEPTS	CATEGORY
MK	<p><i>... uhm maybe the primary challenges in studying English uhm... the right pronunciation of words, using the right grammar, and understanding their idiomatic expression... I really struggle there sometimes in switching from Blaan to English, you really need to be aware of your pronunciation.</i></p> <p><i>Ahh yes, there are always social and cultural challenges that I experience, sometimes in how to adapt to the communication style of different cultures... sometimes we feel embarrassed and afraid that what we're saying might be wrong... because of cultural differences that we are not familiar with.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar awareness. ● Challenges in communication in diverse cultures. ● Challenges in using both first language and second language. ● Afraid of interacting or socializing with diverse cultures. ● Afraid of making mistakes or lack of self-confidence in communicating with others. ● Lack of self-confidence in communicating with others. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Negative attitude towards communication with others because of language barriers. ● Challenges in communication in diverse cultures. ● Lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar awareness.
RB	<p><i>Some of the primary challenges I faced when learning in English because of language barrier is how to pronounce and grammar, the pronunciation of words... especially because there are English that are too hard to pronounce.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar awareness. ● Afraid of interacting or socializing with diverse cultures. ● Challenges in communication in diverse cultures. 	

	<p><i>There really are social or cultural challenges you will face will you will face during language learning, especially if others have a different understanding or pronunciation of sentences, different ways of delivering sentences, and different grammar usage...especially in inter-when interacting with other people or those other have, those from different cultures, there are various dialects and language to consider, especially when learning English... If you are thought differently or understand things differently, misunderstandings can occur, leading to language barriers when socializing.</i></p>		
<p>AB</p>	<p><i>... the primary challenges that I face when it comes in learning English because of language barrier is discovering new words... there are unfamiliar words to me that... I can't barely understand.</i></p> <p><i>Yes, there are a lot of social and cultural challenges that I face during my English learning just like... when communicating to the other tribes.... I am struggling to communicate because.... there are a lot of word that is forbidden to use because of their culture.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of vocabulary awareness. ● Challenges in communication in diverse cultures 	

AS	<p><i>... the primary challenges I face when learning English because of language barriers are the grammar rules like verb tenses.</i></p> <p><i>Yes, there are several social and cultural challenges associated with language barriers that I encounter during English language learning like difficulties in communicating in English.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facing learning English due to language barriers, particularly regarding grammar rules such as verb tenses and prepositions. • Difficulties in communication, isolation, hindered integration into English-speaking communities. 	
EQ	<p><i>The main challenges I faced is understanding the nuances, idioms, and colloquialism of English...</i></p> <p><i>There are any social or cultural challenges associated with language barriers that I have encountered during my English... language can sometimes uhm... lead to misunderstandings or difficulties in... communicating effectively in different people...</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of awareness in parts and complexities of the English language. • Understand the purpose of learning English. • Positive approach in learning English. • Challenges in communication in diverse cultures. 	

Three emergent themes were generated from the data in Table 2: 1) Negative attitude and approach towards communication with others because of language barriers; 2) challenges in communication in diverse cultures; and 3) lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar awareness.

The first theme was a negative attitude and approach towards communication with others because of language barriers. Participants MK and RB shared how they were afraid to communicate using English. Participant AS stated that difficulties in communicating led her to hinder and isolate integration into the English-speaking community.

Additionally, the second theme was challenges in communication in diverse cultures. Participants MK, RB, and AB shared that communication with other people or with people from different cultures challenged them and prevented them from using English. As Participant MK stated, adapting the communication style of different cultures was one of the challenges she faced in learning English because there are different pronunciations of words depending on the culture,

which might lead to miscommunication. In the same scenario, participant RB also recalled that one of her challenges in learning English in terms of language barriers is having different pronunciations, different ways of delivering sentences, and different grammar usage.

Moreover, the third theme was a lack of vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar awareness. Participants MK and RB shared their experiences of struggling to learn English, especially in the pronunciation of words, vocabulary, and use of grammar. They stated that they are struggling with pronouncing some words, when to use unfamiliar words, and grammar rules.

Buarqoub (2019) stated that language barriers can lead to various miscommunication issues, including misunderstandings, misinformation, and uncertainty. This aligns with the challenges of participants MK, RB, and EQ, a full-blooded blaang, and participants AB and AS, a half-blooded blaang who stated inadequate skills as a significant barrier to communication and cultural integration.

Table 3. Coping mechanisms of Blaang students in learning English in terms of language barriers.

PARTICIPANTS CODE	SIGNIFICANT STATEMENT	CONCEPTS	CATEGORY
MK	<p><i>... strategy to overcome the language barrier... to listen to or watch videos related to the English language, socialize with people, or talk to your close friends using English... using language learning apps and practicing reading and writing in English.</i></p> <p><i>Ah, yes, and we should use external assistance such as English tutorial processes, language exchange programs, and online resources like YouTube and educational apps.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Seeking a strategy to overcome the language barriers. ● Acknowledgement of materials helped to improve learning. ● Seeking external assistance and support systems through online platforms like Google and asking instructors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Positive approach to overcoming language barriers. ● Value the importance of asking for help.
RB	<p><i>I read books and try to research some vocabulary to increase my vocabulary and improve my grammar... when I encounter unfamiliar words or words that I don't know how to pronounce or use in a sentence, I research them.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Seeking strategy to overcome the language barriers. ● Acknowledgement of materials helped to improve learning. ● Seeking external assistance and support systems through online 	

	<p><i>Google and the Cici app are what help me when ahh I'm studying English. They are ahh effective and can truly help me a lot.</i></p>	<p>platforms like Google and asking instructors.</p>
AB	<p>The strategies that I use... is sometimes I do research on it and I ask some of my peers in order to understand.</p> <p>Yes, and it is true interaction it is my support system to learning and cope of the language barriers.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Seeking a strategy to overcome the language barriers. ● Understanding the purpose of interaction or communication with other cultures. ● Value the importance of asking for help
AS	<p>The strategies I use to overcome language barriers while learning English are using some app like TikTok, Netflix, YouTube... I use them to watch some educational videos or tips on how to be a good speaker or how to improve your English.</p> <p>Yes, I sought and external assistance or support systems ... to cope with language barriers... some of this are asking on the online platforms like google and also I asked one of my instructors if I am having difficulties of uhm learning English.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Using various apps like TikTok, Netflix, and YouTube to watch educational videos and improve your English skills. ● Seeking external assistance and support systems through online platforms like Google and asking instructors. ● Value the importance of asking for help
EQ	<p>The strategies that I used to overcome language barriers while learning language or... first, when it comes to my pronunciation, I do.... practice reading, I do use interpreters or</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Seeking strategy to overcome the language barriers. ● Acknowledgement of friends, teachers, and materials helped to improve learning.

	<p>translators when it comes to my grammar.</p> <p>Yes, I have sought any external assistance or support system to cope with language barriers such as my friends, my teachers... also I do research with the google... that it is very effective or helpful for me for me to be able to deal with the language barrier.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Seeking external assistance and support systems through online platforms like Google and asking instructors. ● Value the importance of asking for help. 	
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Two emergent themes were generated from the data in Table 3: 1) Positive approach to overcoming language barriers; and 2) valuing the importance of asking for help.

The first theme was a positive approach to overcoming language barriers. All five participants shared their strategies for learning the English language while overcoming language barriers as BSED-English Blaan students. Participants MK, RB, AB, AS, and EQ stated that if they encounter unfamiliar words or sentences, they use external assistance to help them or to assist them with the unfamiliar words and sentences. Teriu (2012, as cited in Elaga & Ozad, 2017) emphasizes the adaptive methods international students employ to navigate language barriers in cross-cultural communication. This includes strategies like "pretending," which involves adapting conversational tactics to maintain face and facilitate effective communication despite linguistic challenges. This concept corresponds with the proactive approaches stated by participants MK, RB, and EQ, a full-blooded blaan, and participants AB and AS, a half-blooded blaan in their efforts to overcome language barriers and enhance their English proficiency. Participants MK and AS also shared how helpful watching educational videos on YouTube, Netflix, or any other online platforms can be for learning English in terms of language barriers.

Additionally, participants RB and EQ shared that reading books helps them learn English and overcome language barriers. Through interaction, participant AB was able to overcome the language barrier in learning English because it allowed her to practice using unfamiliar words and sentences. In the same scenario, participant MK also recalled that interaction helped her learn English.

Moreover, the second theme was valuing the importance of asking for help. Participants RB, AB, AS, and EQ shared that they ask for help from others, such as friends and instructors, to help them overcome the language barriers and learn English. Participant MK stated that watching English tutorials, language exchange programs, YouTube, and educational apps are effective in helping her improve her pronunciation, grammar, and fluency in English. Participants AB and EQ stated that they browsed Google to see if there were words or sentences that they weren't familiar with.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, this study reveals significant challenges faced by Blaan students in learning English, particularly in comprehending and pronouncing words, which often leads to misunderstandings and communication barriers. It underscores the importance of providing

support and tools to alleviate these language difficulties and enhance understanding of diverse cultures. The research suggests that activities such as reading, social interaction, and utilizing online platforms like Google, YouTube, and TikTok, along with watching subtitled movies, can effectively improve vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation skills. These resources facilitate a broader linguistic knowledge base. By leveraging these tools, educators and Blaan students can collaborate to foster an inclusive and supportive learning environment conducive to successful English language acquisition and communication.

Recommendations

This study revealed the challenges BSED-English Blaan students face in learning English because of language barriers. Thus, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

To the Students. This study encourages students to read books more often in the library or in any books available to help them widen their vocabulary, use educational online platforms to assist them in learning English, and practice socializing with diverse cultures using the English language to practice communicating with others and using the language.

To Teachers. This study encourages teachers to show encouragement to their students to speak, share their opinions and thoughts, and utilize a friendly environment in class to lessen their fear of speaking English. Teachers may also utilize reading books and provide more activities using their macro skills to improve their knowledge and speaking skills.

To the School Administration. This study encourages the school administration to strictly implement the English-only policy, especially for English students, to help them practice their vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. It also encourages providing more books in the library, especially English books, to help students with their problems in terms of grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation.

To Future Researchers. This study may serve as a basis for future researchers to further study the lived experiences of BSED-English in terms of language barriers in a larger group to determine if the same findings will be established.

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